

Diversity of urban of birds of Dhirkot, Pakistan

Saima Azad¹ and Maryam Faiz^{1*}

1. Department of Zoology, Women University of Azad Jammu and Kashmir, Bagh, Pakistan

*Corresponding author e-mail: maryamfaiz1996@gmail.com

SUMMARY

There are a total of 9042 bird species in the globe; more than 668 avian species have been reported in Pakistan. The purpose of this study was to learn about the variety of birds in urban areas. The linear count technique was used to analyze the diversity of birds in urban areas, which was further subdivided into direct and indirect data collection method. For the analysis of data, past software (version 3) was used to find out Dominance Index, Evenness Index, Richness Index, Shannon-wiener Diversity Index, and Simpson Diversity Index. During the present study we noted that a total of 10 avian species observed from district, Dhirkot AJK shown in while diversity indices of urban area were recorded as Dominance (0.5059), Simpson (0.4941), Shannon (1.012), Evenness (0.275) and Margalef (1.363). During the research find that study has high population and but less number of species, evenness and dominance are also low in the study area.

Keywords: Birds, Himalaya, Simpson, Pakistan

Citation: Azad, S., M. Faiz. 2023. Diversity of urban of birds of Dhirkot, Pakistan. International Journal of Forest Sciences. 3: 18-23.

Received: January, 2023; **Accepted:** February, 2023

INTRODUCTION

In the world, high diversity i.e. 9042 avian species (Sibley and Monroe, 1990; Sibley and Monroe Jr, 1993) and in Pakistan more than 660 species are documented (Grimmett, 1998; Mirza and Wasiq, 2007). Six bio-geographic regions present in world, while some parts of Ethiopian, Palearctic and Oriental are present in Pakistan. Pakistan is connected to the Arabian Sea because its northern tip is located in the stable snow landscape of Pamir in the huge Mountains. The mountain ranges in the north, west, and northwest are a confluence of three mountain ranges: the Hindukush, the Himalayas, and the Karakorum (Khan, 2006). The Pakistan has more than 225 wetlands and 19 Ramsar sites; largest river system present in Pakistan. Pakistan has large variety of animals due to abrupt changes in elevation (Altaf *et al.*, 2014).

Human involvement enhance the accessibility of food for animals such as omnivores, insects, granivores, and nectivores get food from waste vegetables (Poague *et al.*, 2000), scavenger as well as herbivores get food from waste materials (Shwartz *et al.*, 2008). Varieties of trees, herbs and shrubs highly impacts resources of food; aliens floral species have smaller quantity of insect than local floral species, while parks and gardens in urban have high feeding places (Parsons *et al.*, 2006).

Birds are excellent indicators of changes in environmental (Babar and Kanwal, 2021), many flights birds can long distance and short distance migrate and barriers cannot stop to birds. Though, awareness is increasing in the human being about pollution and its impacts; but there is very few material or literature on the impacts of pollutant and pollution on each landscape (Furness and Greenwood, 1993). Avian species are used in the landscape study because the birds are environmental indicators for all landscapes (Becker, 1989; Becker *et al.*, 1993; Furness, 1993); (Lemly, 1997; Pain *et al.*, 1998; Eens *et al.*, 1999; Tanabe, 2002). Therefore this research work was planned to learn about the variety of birds in the urban ecology of Dhirkot, Pakistan.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

AREA DESCRIPTION

Dhirkot is a located in Pakistan. The entire area is hilly in topography. The region is part of the lower Himalayas zone. Coniferous woods cover the majority of the highlands. Nonetheless, various additional streams go through this landscape (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Map of the Study area district Dhirkot, Azad Jammu Kashmir (Farooq *et al.*, 2019).

METHODOLOGY

The linear count method was applied to know the variety of species (from March 2017 to February 2018), which was additionally divide up into direct data collection method (physical and voices count) and indirect data collection method (interviews of native people, dead bodies, pictures).

ANALYSIS OF DATA

The past software (version 3) was applied for the data analysis to get diversity indices i.e. Dominance Index, Evenness Index, Richness Index, Shannon-wiener Diversity Index, and Simpson Diversity Index.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The current study was carried out to discover the bird fauna of Dhirkot using direct and indirect approaches. Indirect method was also consist of questionnaire. The questionnaire filled by the respondents of local area. The respondents profile was male and female Muslims.

Table 1: Details of the present observation and current status of avian fauna diversity of district Dhirkot.

Sr.	Scientific name	Common name	Authority	Dist.	Status	Urban
1.	<i>Acridotheres tristis</i>	Common Myna	(Linnaeus, 1766)	R	LC	500
2.	<i>Columba hodgsonii</i>	Speckled Wood Pigeon	(Vigors, 1832)	R	LC	1
3.	<i>Columba livia</i>	Common Pigeon	(Gmelin, 1789)	R	LC	2
4.	<i>Corvus splendens</i>	House Crow	(Vieillot, 1817)	R	LC	150
5.	<i>Milvus migrans</i>	Black Kite	(Boddaert, 1783)	R	LC	5
6.	<i>Passer domesticus</i>	House Sparrow	(Linnaeus, 1758)	SV	LC	10
7.	<i>Psittacula eupatria</i>	Alexander Parakeet	(Linnaeus, 1766)	R	LC	30
8.	<i>Psittacula krameri</i>	Rose-ringed Parakeet	(Scopoli, 1769)	R	LC	35
9.	<i>Spilopelia chinensis</i>	Spotted Dove	(Scopoli, 1786)	SV	LC	2
10.	<i>Streptopelia orientalis</i>	Oriental Turtle Dove	(Latham, 1790)	SV	LC	2
Totals						737

Note: R (resident), SV (spring visitor), LC, (Least Count)

Table 2: The diversity indices of the avian fauna of district Dhirkot.

Diversity Indices	Urban
Species (abbreviated as Spp)	10
Population (abbreviated as P)	737
Dominance Index (abbreviated as D)	0.5059
Simpson Diversity Index (abbreviated as S)	0.4941
Shannon-wiener Diversity Index (abbreviated as H')	1.012
Evenness Index (abbreviated as E)	0.275
Richness Index (abbreviated as R)	1.363

Note: P (population), D (dominance), S (Simpson), H (Shannon), E (evenness), R (richness) and SPP (species).

During the present study we noted that a total of 10 avian species observed from district, Dhirkot AJK shown in (Table 1) while diversity indices of urban area were recorded as Dominance (0.5059), Simpson (0.4941), Shannon (1.012), Evenness (0.275) and Margalef (1.363) as shown in table 2. Batool *et al.* (2022) noted 37 avian species from rural and urban ecosystems of Khanewal district. Lots of avian species such as can be found in a variety of habitats like intense urbanization, low urbanization, and rural ecosystems. Ring-necked doves are commonly found at trees in urban sites. Human residential areas provides shelter and food (Ali *et al.*, 2018). These all factors show that human play a vital rule to dispersal of species (Altaf, 2021). Birds are documented from different parts of Pakistan; district Haripur, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (Jadoon *et al.*, 2019), district Sargodha, Pakistan (Ashraf *et al.*, 2018), tropical thorn forest, Punjab (Altaf *et al.*, 2018), district of the Badin (Ali *et al.*, 2018), head Khanki, Punjab (Altaf *et al.*, 2013), Gujranwala, Punjab, Pakistan (Altaf *et al.*, 2012), Kallar Kahar Lake district Chakwal (Rais *et al.*, 2010), head Qadirabad, Gujranwala, Pakistan (Altaf, 2010), Uchalli Wetlands Complex, Punjab (Ali, 2005; Ashraf *et al.*, 2019), Khanewal, Punjab, Pakistan (Batool *et al.*, 2022), Chakar, Hattian Bala district, Azad Jammu and Kashmir (Mughal *et al.*, 2020) and coastal of Sindh, Pakistan (Ali *et al.*, 2020).

CONCLUSIONS

During the research noted that study has high population and but less number of species, evenness and dominance are also low in the study area. Total 10 species are documented while species are abundant and can be seen easily.

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